

A Generalized Precedence Test for Multivariate Lifetime Data

Chase Holcombe¹

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of South Alabama, Mobile, AL, USA

Abstract

This paper develops a generalized precedence test for comparing multivariate lifetime distributions. The classical precedence test, originally proposed for univariate life-testing problems, is reinterpreted in terms of statistically equivalent blocks, providing a natural foundation for multivariate extension. The resulting procedure remains exactly distribution-free under the null hypothesis of equal distributions and is compatible with Type II censoring, a desirable property in reliability settings where early termination of experiments reduces testing time and cost. A simulated case study of industrial cooling units illustrates the method, with lifetimes modeled for two dependent components: a compressor module and an electronic control board. The example highlights how the generalized test accommodates dependence between lifetimes while retaining intuitive interpretability. The proposed framework offers a practical nonparametric alternative to parametric multivariate tests that rely on restrictive distributional assumptions.

Key Words: Distribution-free, Reliability data, Multivariate lifetimes, Type II censoring

1. Introduction

Modern reliability studies often involve multivariate or high-dimensional observations where components within a system fail according to distinct but dependent mechanisms. A recurring challenge in these settings is to compare multivariate lifetime distributions across two populations, often a control group and a treatment or prototype group, when standard parametric assumptions are either doubtful or unverifiable.

Consider the following example, drawn from industrial reliability testing. Suppose that a manufacturer of industrial cooling units is evaluating a new design intended for deployment in harsh environments such as high-humidity industrial facilities. Each unit contains two critical components: a compressor module and an electronic control board. For each manufactured unit, two failure times are recorded, failure times for the compressor and for the control board. The manufacturer has a control or reference dataset of size $n = 50$ corresponding to units field-tested under standard environmental conditions (Group A), and a smaller dataset of size $m = 15$ corresponding to the new prototype units tested under accelerated environmental stress (Group B). Engineers are concerned that early signs of degradation may appear in both components under the new conditions, and they wish to evaluate whether these stressed units tend to fail earlier than their field-tested counterparts. Because both components operate within the same enclosure and are exposed to common environmental stressors, it is reasonable to assume that their lifetimes are positively correlated, reflecting the presence of shared shocks or degradation mechanisms.

This simple scenario illustrates a common structure in applied reliability analysis where multiple, possibly dependent, lifetimes are to be tested. In this case, the engineer is interested in a directional testing objective, to determine whether the observational units in the prototype group tend to experience earlier failure. It also exposes the limitations of existing methods. Approaches that involve assuming a parametric form for the lifetime distribution, such as assuming independent or

correlated Weibull lifetimes or multivariate lognormal models, impose strong structural forms on the data-generating process that may be difficult to justify in applied settings. Additionally, classical multivariate tests based on Hotelling's T^2 or spatial depth may fail to maintain the desired testing significance level for finite samples. Similarly, multivariate methods based on spatial signs and ranks such as those discussed by Oja and Randles (2004) are exactly distribution-free only for elliptical distributions, an assumption that is likely violated in the lifetime setting.

In the univariate case, an appealing alternative is the class of precedence-type tests (Balakrishnan and Ng, 2006). These tests, which may be considered as two-sample extensions of the sign test, evaluate how many observations from one sample “precede” an order statistic from the other sample. While intuitive and powerful for detecting shift alternatives, traditional precedence tests are explicitly based on order statistics and are thus limited to univariate data. One possible approach in the multivariate reliability setting would be to perform component-wise precedence tests with some adjusted significance level using, for example, a Bonferroni or Šidák correction. For positively correlated data, such an approach could be very conservative, severely limiting the power of the test.

In this paper, we consider a multivariate generalization of the precedence test using a framework based on statistically equivalent blocks (se-blocks). These blocks partition the sample space into regions that, under the null hypothesis of identical population distributions, the probability contents of the se-blocks are jointly distributed following the *Dirichlet*(**1**) distribution. This structure allows one to define precedence-type statistics as functions of the number of observations from one sample falling into earlier se-blocks partitioned by the other sample, as opposed to preceding some order statistic. This framework preserves exact distribution-free properties. This generalized precedence test, suggested by Holcombe (2025), has not yet been explored, carefully considered, or illustrated in the reliability setting.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces se-blocks and shows how the classical univariate precedence test can be represented in terms of block frequencies. Section 3 presents a multivariate generalization, including the construction of se-blocks in \mathbb{R}^p for any $p \in \mathbb{N}$. Section 4 applies the test to simulated data based on the cooling unit failure example. Section 5 concludes with discussion of extensions.

2. SE-Blocks and the Precedence Test in the Univariate Case

2.1 Precedence Test Background

The precedence test was introduced in the context of univariate life-testing problems (Gumbel & von Schelling, 1950; Nelson, 1963) for two independent samples, $X_1, \dots, X_m \sim F$ and $Y_1, \dots, Y_n \sim G$ from continuous distributions, which we may denote as the control and treatment or prototype group, respectively. The precedence statistic takes the number of X observations that are less than the j -th order statistic from the Y sample, $Y_{(j:n)}$. The statistic may be written as,

$$T_j = \sum_{i=1}^m I(X_i < Y_{(j:n)}),$$

Equation (1)

where $I(\cdot)$ is the indicator function. Under the assumption of identical distributions, $F = G$, T_j follows the negative hypergeometric distribution with mass function,

$$P(T_j = t) = \frac{\binom{t+j-1}{t} \binom{m-t+n-j}{m-t}}{\binom{m+n}{m}}, t = 0, 1, \dots, m.$$

Equation (2)

Since the distribution of the test statistic does not depend on the underlying data distribution under the null hypothesis of identical distributions, the test is exactly distribution-free. Relatively larger values of T_j provide evidence that the X (control) population tends to have smaller values than the Y (prototype) population, or equivalently that the control group tends to fail earlier. The inverse is also true, so that smaller values of T_j provide evidence that the failure times of the control are larger than the failure times for the prototypes. This procedure may be used effectively for location shifts, against which the test is consistent (Balakrishnan and Ng, 2006, p. 54). An additional advantage of this setup is its natural alignment with Type II censoring in life-testing. Since information from the prototype group relevant to the testing procedure is contained in the j -th order statistic, $Y_{(j)}$, the experiment can be terminated at the time of the j -th failure. All subsequent test units are censored, but the statistic remains well-defined. Thus, the procedure is compatible with standard reliability study designs where early stopping is desirable.

2.2 SE-Blocks

Although traditionally defined in terms of order statistics, the precedence test can be re-expressed more generally using the concept of se-blocks, as shown by Holcombe (2025). First, we briefly review the definition of an se-block. The genesis of the se-block can be traced back to Wald (1943) in his generalization of Wilks's (1941) tolerance interval method, which was developed using the distribution of order statistics. The term "statistically equivalent block" was then coined by Tukey (1947) in a further generalization of this work. In fact, se-blocks may be considered generalizations of the area between adjacent order statistics. For the sample Y_1, \dots, Y_n in the univariate setting, the most natural partitioning of the se-blocks B_1, \dots, B_{n+1} would be so that $B_1 = (-\infty, Y_{(1:n)}]$, $B_{n+1} = (Y_{(n:n)}, \infty)$, and $B_i = (Y_{(i-1:n)}, Y_{(i:n)})$ for $i = 2, \dots, n$. Note that the assignment of the value $Y_{(i:n)}$ to B_i as opposed to B_{i+1} is immaterial since the population is assumed to be continuous. The distribution of the probability content of the blocks, equivalent with the distribution of the area between *Uniform*(0,1) order statistics, is jointly *Dirichlet*(**1**) and marginally *Beta*(1, n) (Gibbons and Chakraborti, 2014, p. 38-46). From this, it is easy to see that the precedence statistic may be written as,

$$T_j = \sum_{i=1}^m I \left(X_i \in \bigcup_{k=1}^j B_k \right),$$

Equation (3)

which is equivalent with the form given in Equation (1). In the two-sample setting, the number of X observations falling in some se-block B_i may be called the i -th block frequency, denoted R_i . So, in terms of the block frequencies, T_j may be expressed equivalently as,

$$T_j = \sum_{i=1}^j R_i.$$

Equation (4)

Amazingly, when se-blocks are partitioned in higher dimension, the null distribution of the probability content is unchanged (Tukey, 1947). Thus, in any dimension p , the precedence test statistic may be calculated as in Equation (4) and maintain the same negative hypergeometric distribution, as in Equation (2). This reinterpretation of the precedence test statistic highlights that the precedence test is not inherently tied to the natural one-dimensional ordering of the real line. Instead, it is a special case of a test based on block frequency, where the "precedence" region is defined by the lowest ordered blocks partitioned by one of the samples. This perspective provides a natural path to multivariate generalization (Holcombe, 2025). The next section develops this extension.

3. SE-Block partitions in the Multivariate Setting

In the univariate setting, a unique ordering along the real number line exists, which leads to the natural partitioning of se-blocks discussed in Section 2. However, in the multivariate setting, no unique ordering exists. In fact, there are infinitely many ways one could partition se-blocks in this setting. One such way is the so-called “stair step” partitioning method (Holcombe, 2025). It may be seen that this method is advantageous in the reliability setting. Suppose now that the two samples $\mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_m$ and $\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_n$ are composed p -dimensional vectors of lifetimes such that $\mathbf{Y}_i = (Y_{i,1}, \dots, Y_{i,p})$. As in the univariate case, we let the \mathbf{Y} sample, corresponding to the treatment or prototype group, be the partitioning sample. Following the stair step method, the se-blocks may be partitioned algorithmically. The first se-block is set to be the area in \mathbb{R}^p bounded above on the axis corresponding to the first lifetime by the minimum observed lifetime among $Y_{1,1}, \dots, Y_{n,1}$. The vector of lifetimes used to partition the se-block, namely the vector containing the minimum lifetime among the first component, is then removed and the procedure is repeated with the remaining $n - 1$ vectors and the remaining area of \mathbb{R}^p that has not yet been partitioned. The process is continued, returning to the first component after an se-block has been partitioned among the p -th vector component, until n se-blocks are partitioned. The final se-block, B_{n+1} is set to be the remaining area.

To formalize the procedure, we further define sets S_1, \dots, S_n that are subsets of $\{\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_n\}$. Let $S_{i,k}$ denote the set of k -th component lifetimes in the set S_i . Further, let $bd(A)$ denote the set of boundary points for a set A . Then, we have $S_1 = \{\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_m\}$ and,

$$S_i = \{s \in \{\mathbf{Y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_m\} : s \notin bd(B_l), l = 1, \dots, i - 1\},$$

Equation (5)

for $i = 2, \dots, n$. So, the first se-block is partitioned such that,

$$B_1 = \{c \in \mathbb{R}^p; c_1 < \min(S_{1,1})\}.$$

Equation (6)

Then, the i -th se-block is partitioned as,

$$B_i = \left\{ c \in \mathbb{R}^p; c_k < \min(S_{i,k}), c \notin \bigcup_{l=1}^{i-1} B_l \right\},$$

Equation (7)

where $k = ((i - 1) \bmod p) + 1$.

One potential drawback of this partitioning method is immediately evident, the method is not invariant to the permutation in the variable or component ordering (Holcombe and Chakraborti, 2024). We must carefully note that the permutation ordering does not change the theoretical null performance. Nonetheless, the fact that the relative ordering imposed among the vector components may impact the exact partitioning of the se-blocks, and thus the block frequencies and observed significance level for the generalized precedence test, is undesirable. Though this is a possibility, it may be noted that in many cases, the precedence region formed by the se-blocks B_1, \dots, B_j may be only slightly impacted, if at all.

As stated at the beginning of the section, there are infinitely many ways to partition se-blocks in higher dimension. The stair step method, however, holds several advantages in the reliability setting, particularly when used to construct a precedence region for the precedence test. Importantly, the se-block construction is scale invariant. Also, relatively lower numbered se-blocks are partitioned using earlier failures. So, under the alternative hypothesis of a location shift or stochastic dominance, this means that failures among the non-partitioning sample occurring in lower se-blocks support the hypothesis that the non-partitioning sample experiences shorter lifetimes on average, with the

inverse also being true. Finally, when used in the hypothesis testing context, this construction is appropriate for certain types of censoring. We illustrate this point in Section 4.

4. Illustrative Example

To illustrate the generalized precedence test in the multivariate setting using the stair step partitioning method, we return to the motivating example. A simulated sample of size $m = 50$ bivariate vectors corresponding to the failure times in hours for the compressor module and control board in the control group were drawn from a bivariate Weibull distribution with common shape parameter $\beta = 1.5$, marginal scale parameters 1000 and 1200, and positive dependence induced through a Gumbel copula with parameter $\theta = 2$. A corresponding prototype sample of size $n = 15$ was generated with the same shape and dependence structure, but with reduced scale parameters of 700 and 900 to reflect accelerated degradation under stressed conditions. The lifetimes for both groups are displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Bivariate lifetime vectors containing failure times for the compressor module and the control board in both the control and prototype samples.

To perform the generalized precedence test, we select j , construct the precedence region using the partitioning method from Section 3 and then calculate the precedence statistic as in Equation (4). While the choice of j does not affect the validity of the test under the null hypothesis, it can influence sensitivity to different types of shifts. In reliability applications, smaller values of j are especially appealing, as they permit more extreme Type II censoring. Thus, when comparing a treatment or prototype group with a control group that has already been tested, choosing a smaller j allows the study to conclude earlier without compromising the validity of the test. For the multivariate case in dimension p , it is important to maintain $j \geq p$ so that the test is sensitive to shifts in each component. For the present example, we set $j = 4$, which avoids relying exclusively on the minimum failures that may unduly influence the statistic.

Given $j = 4$, only the first four se-blocks, B_1, \dots, B_4 , must be partitioned using the prototype sample. These four se-blocks compose the precedence region. Given that the Compressor Lifetime is ordered as the “first” component, these se-blocks are constructed using Equations (5) and (6) and are displayed along with the prototype sample lifetimes in Figure 2. In fact, had the ordering of the components been reversed, these se-blocks would have been partitioned as in Figure 3. Though the individual se-blocks are defined differently, the precedence region composing the union of these sets is identical, showing that for this example, the ordering of the components does not impact the test results.

Figure 2: The bivariate prototype lifetime vectors overlaid with the first four partitioned se-blocks with the compressor module lifetime ordered as the first component.

Figure 3: The bivariate prototype lifetime vectors overlaid with the first four partitioned se-blocks with the control board lifetime ordered as the first component.

Now that the precedence region is constructed, the control data may be overlaid for comparison. The precedence statistic is calculated by summing the block frequencies, as in Equation (4). This is equivalent to counting the number of bivariate control group observations that are inside the precedence region. Graphically, in Figure 4, this corresponds to counting the number of points in the shaded region. So, we have $T_j = 3$. Since the engineers in this example are interested in evaluating whether these prototype units tend to fail earlier than the control units, the one-tailed test

is appropriate. A p-value may then be calculated, using the distribution in Equation (2), as $P(T_j \leq 3) = 0.044$. Thus, at the conventional $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level, the result is that the null hypothesis of identical distributions is rejected in favor of the alternative that the prototype units tend to experience earlier failures.

Returning to the question of Type II censoring, we note that despite the fact that the full prototype failure data is displayed in Figures 2 and 3, the experiment could have been stopped and the test performed as soon as the precedence region had been determined. Thus, in this example, the experiment could have been concluded at 323.65 hours, as opposed to waiting the full 1386.62 hours for the final prototype failure.

Figure 4: The control sample bivariate lifetime vectors overlaid with the precedence region constructed using the prototype sample.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, a generalized precedence test for comparing multivariate lifetime distributions constructed using se-blocks is developed and illustrated. This extension retains the exact distribution-free property of the univariate precedence test while enabling applications in higher dimensions, a setting where traditional rank and depth-based methods often rely on asymptotic properties or strong distributional assumptions. Using a simulated reliability example, it is demonstrated how the test can be applied in practice, highlighting both its intuitive interpretation and its natural compatibility with Type II censoring, a common feature of industrial life-testing studies.

The results underscore the utility of the generalized precedence test as a nonparametric alternative in multivariate reliability problems, especially when dependence between component lifetimes must be accommodated. Future work may involve finding classes of alternatives against which the test is consistent and extending the test to the case of censoring among both samples.

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